

Received-Makale Geliş Tarihi 20.09.2025
Published-Yayınlanma Tarihi 31.10.2025
Volume-Cilt (Issue-Sayı), ss/pp 12 (124),2247-2257

Review Article / Derleme Makale
10.5281/zenodo.17525138

Dr. Öğretim Üyesi Tuba Özturan

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7099-0076>

Erzincan Binali Yıldırım Üniversitesi, Fen-Edebiyat Fakültesi, Erzincan / TÜRKİYE

ROR Id: <https://ror.org/02h1e8605>

Mapping the Methodological Developments in Dynamic Assessment Research: Insights from Studies in Applied Linguistics

Dinamik Değerlendirme Araştırmalarındaki Metodolojik Gelişmelerin Haritalandırılması: Uygulamalı Dilbilim Alanındaki Çalışmalardan Elde Edilen Bilgiler

ABSTRACT

This systematic review aims to present an overview of dynamic assessment research in language education. With that purpose, the review followed the PRISMA framework, selected the articles carefully through inclusion and exclusion criteria, and coded the included studies following the PICO guidance. Accordingly, the Web of Science research database was employed to search for the related studies. Upon deciding the search terms, articles published from 2015 to 2025 and indexed in SSCI, SSCI-expanded, and AHCI were examined. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 20 articles were included for the review. These articles were then coded thematically, regarding the journal in which they were published, the publication year, the country where the scholars were based, research design, data collection and analysis methods, and participants (their educational level, language setting, and target language). The findings displayed that the included studies appeared in diverse journals. 2022 marked the year when dynamic assessment started to get much attention, but the highest number of articles was in 2025. Scholars were from different countries, yet the USA and Iran were the majority. Mixed-methods research design and experimental research design were mainly adopted. Within this framework, pre- and post-tests and interviews were the primary data collection tools. At the same time, statistical tests (e.g., ANOVA, ANCOVA, t-tests) and thematic coding were the primary data analysis methods. The participants displayed diversity in their educational levels; however, the language setting was mostly limited to foreign languages, with English being the predominant foreign language. The review also presents its implications and limitations.

Keywords: dynamic assessment, language education, systematic review.

ÖZET

Bu sistematik inceleme, dil eğitiminde dinamik değerlendirme araştırmalarına genel bir bakış sunmayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu amaçla, inceleme PRISMA çerçevesini takip etmiş, dahil etme ve hariç tutma kriterleri aracılığıyla makaleleri dikkatlice seçmiş ve dahil edilen çalışmaları PICO kılavuzuna göre kodlamıştır. Buna göre, ilgili çalışmaları aramak için Web of Science araştırma veritabanı kullanıldı. Arama terimleri belirlendikten sonra, 2015 ile 2025 yılları arasında yayınlanan ve SSCI, SSCI-expanded ve AHCI'da indekslenen makaleler incelendi. Dahil etme ve hariç tutma kriterleri uygulandıktan sonra, incelemeye 20 makale dahil edildi. Bu makaleler daha sonra yayımlandıkları dergi, yayın yılı, akademisyenlerin bulunduğu ülke, araştırma tasarımı, veri toplama ve analiz yöntemleri ve katılımcılar (eğitim düzeyleri, dili öğrenme bağlamları ve hedef dilleri) açısından tematik olarak kodlandı. Bulgular, dahil edilen çalışmaların çeşitli dergilerde yayımlandığını gösterdi. 2022, dinamik değerlendirmenin büyük ilgi görmeye başladığı yıl oldu, ancak en fazla makale sayısı 2025'teydi. Araştırmacılar farklı ülkelerden olmakla birlikte, çoğunluğu ABD ve İran'dandı. Karma yöntem araştırma tasarımı ve deneysel araştırma tasarımı esas olarak benimsenmiş olup, bu kapsamda ön ve son testler ile görüşmeler birincil veri toplama araçları, istatistiksel testler (ör. ANOVA, ANCOVA, t-testleri) ve tematik kodlama ise ana veri analiz yöntemleri olarak kullanılmıştır. Katılımcılar eğitim düzeyleri açısından çeşitlilik göstermişlerdir, ancak dil öğrenme ortamı çoğunlukla yabancı dille sınırlı kalmış ve yabancı dil olarak çoğunlukla İngilizce kullanılmıştır. İnceleme, sonuçları ve sınırlılıkları da sunmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: dinamik değerlendirme, dil eğitimi, sistematik derleme.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic Assessment (DA) is a learning-oriented assessment method that blends instruction with assessment in a single cooperative effort between teachers and students (Poehner, 2008). Accordingly, teachers are responsible for assessing each learner's matured abilities, needs, and emerging abilities through goal-oriented dialogic interaction. In this context, matured abilities refer to the Zone of Actual Development (ZAD), while emerging skills under guidance refer to the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) (Poehner, 2008; Vygotsky, 1978). Both teachers and students are active agents in this dialogic interaction process because teachers assess the students' ZAD and ZPD by employing an implicit-to-explicit feedback loop and analyzing each student's responsiveness to the feedback provided (Lantolf & Poehner, 2004).

Grounding on Vygotsky's (1978) Sociocultural Theory (SCT) and Feuerstein et al.'s (2010) Mediated Learning Experience (MLE), DA asserts that learning is a socially co-constructed process; therefore, having a social interaction with teachers, more-able peers, or parents create a learning environment that new input might serve as a mediated input for learners through social interaction (Feuerstein et al., 2010; Vygostky, 1978).

In a school context, teachers can engage in social interaction either through simultaneous interaction based on learners' errors (interactionist DA) or by adopting a pre-defined graduated feedback loop, as described in Aljaafreh and Lantolf's study (1994) (interventionist DA) (Poehner, 2008). In both cases, teachers are supposed to initiate a DA session, providing the most implicit feedback to elicit learners' ZAD and needs. Then, by fine-tuning feedback (from an implicit to an explicit loop), teachers continue DA sessions to trace learners' microgenesis (tiny moves of improvement), transfer abilities of their emerging skills, and any potential for resistance to chance, all of which display ZPD (Lidz & Gindis, 2003; Poehner, 2008). Within this nature DA differs from other static assessment approaches because not only does a fine-tuned feedback loop enhance instruction, but learners' responses are also assessed through their verbalization. Also, efforts to determine cognitive growth and learning potential (present-to-future) are at the forefront (Poehner & Lantolf, 2003; Shrestha, 2020).

DA has been employed and researched in language education, mainly in L2 writing studies. For example, it was found to be a practical instruction for teaching linguistic features (Davin & Donato, 2013). Also DA had a long-term development in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) (Infante & Poehner, 2019; Özturan & Shrestha, 2025) and in academic writing contexts (Özturan & Uysal, 2022; Shrestha, 2020). Özturan et al. (2023), on the other hand, investigated students' perceptions of adopting DA in an EFL writing class. The findings highlighted DA's power in enhancing personalized and growth-oriented learning, increasing motivation, and reducing anxiety. Davin and Herazo (2020) explored teachers' perspectives and presented that it could be challenging to provide consistent DA sessions, particularly in multilingual classes.

Few systematic reviews were conducted to enlighten dynamic assessment and language education. For example, Dixon et al. (2022) investigated the potential contributions of DA to reading disorder by reviewing 14 articles. Subsequently, Dixon et al. (2023) focused on the predictive value of DA on reading improvement, examining 18 studies published between 1992 and 2020. The findings of both studies demonstrated the power of DA to reveal individual differences in reading development, which were difficult to explain through static assessment. Xia et al. (2024), on the other hand, focused on DA and vocabulary learning in their systematic review. They selected 14 studies that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the findings indicated that the impact of DA on vocabulary learning, particularly in a second language context, remained unclear. In addition to these three reviews, which have focused on a particular language skill and DA there is one review based on DA and language education in general. Li and Li (2015) reviewed 25 studies and presented a detailed section on key findings in their research. Accordingly DA had the potential to enhance L2 (second and foreign language) improvement; the research agenda of the related studies included both interactionist and interventionist DA methods; small sample groups were widely adopted, grammar and reading were commonly investigated; group DA might be a better alternative; and computers might serve as an assistant tool for teachers employing DA.

It is clear that the number of studies is quite limited, and primarily they focused on one language skill. Although there is one review that focused on language education in general and DA it dates back to 2015. Concerning these reviews' contributions and limitations, this systematic review aims to enlighten the field by reviewing DA and language education-oriented studies published between 2015 and 2025 and indexed in SSCI (Social Sciences Citation Index), SSCI-expanded, and AHCI (Arts and Humanities Citation Index). By doing so, I aim to answer the following research question and hope to present a complete understanding of DA in language education:

1. What are the research contexts in the dynamic assessment and language education-oriented studies?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Dataset

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was employed to search for the related studies to be included for this review because the PRISMA framework provides transparent and reliable guidance for the reviews (Page et al., 2021). Moreover, Chong and Plonsky (2021) recommended some crucial steps to search for and select studies to enhance the validity of the reviews. Within this nature, four steps guided this study:

- 1) Identify databases and search terms,
- 2) Search for the relevant studies,
- 3) Screen these studies according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria,
- 4) Check the eligibility of the selected studies.

To avoid a strict selection process through search terms, two search term lists were created. Afterwards, the asterisk (*) was used to reduce spelling errors and enhance spelling flexibility (e.g., *learning vs learner*). Furthermore, Boolean Operators (AND and OR) were adopted to increase the search results. At the end, the following terms were used for searching for the relevant studies:

(“dynamic assess”) AND (“language learn*” OR “language educat*” OR “language teach*”)*

The Web of Science (WoS) research database was selected to find the relevant studies on dynamic assessment and language education. I selected this research database intentionally to access studies with peer-reviewed content and established quality control (Aryadoust & Zhang, 2025). Using the search terms and the WoS database and filtering the advanced search panel to “SSCI, SSCI-Expanded, and AHCI” indexed, I looked for the relevant studies published between 2015 and 2025. The initial results yielded 36 articles. Four studies could not be accessed, so they were removed. Then, 32 studies were screened using the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as mentioned below.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Articles indexed in SSCI, SSCI-expanded, AHCI	Articles indexed in ESCI, Scopus, and others
Articles published between 2015 and 2025	Articles published before 2015
Articles based on dynamic assessment and language education	Articles not based on dynamic assessment or language education
Articles written in English	Articles written in other languages

The studies (n=32) were screened upon reading their titles and abstracts. Twelve studies focused solely on language education and did not have the scope to rely on DA; therefore, I removed them. All these steps were meticulously noted on the PRISMA diagram (Figure 1), which was also presented below. At the end, 20 studies were included in the review and selected for the coding process.

* These articles could not be accessed.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram

2.2. Coding

Following Chong and Plonksy's (2021) PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) framework, a coding scheme (Figure 2) was created to answer the research question. Accordingly, there was one main category: research context. In the research context, six sub-categories—journal, year, country, research design, data collection and analysis, and participants—were created to present the results thematically.

As for the coding of the included studies, the two-cycle method was employed (Charmaz, 2014; Shen & Chong, 2023). This method presents guidance with an initial coding followed by focused coding. Clearly, in the initial coding stage, the coders search for the related words/phrases germane to findings, and then these codes are inserted under the relevant themes/categories. To increase the consistency of the coding, all codes were cross-checked in two rounds.

Figure 2. Coding Scheme

2.3. Ethical Permission

This is a systematic review study, so it is not obliged to present an ethical permission form because no humans were included in the review. Merely articles for which copyright belongs to the journal were subjected to content analysis.

3. FINDINGS

3.1. Research Context

The research question aimed to reveal the research context under six sub-categories. One of these categories was to show the distribution of articles by journal, and Table 2 presents the journals with their distribution numbers. Accordingly, the articles were published in diverse journals, including the Modern Language Journal, TESOL Quarterly, Reading and Writing, among others, and Computer Assisted Language Learning was the journal in which the most, four articles, appeared, followed by Interactive Learning Environment (N=2) and Education and Information Technologies (N=2).

Table 2. Distribution of Articles by Journal

<i>Journal</i>	<i>N</i>
Computer-Assisted Language Learning	4
Interactive Learning Environments	2
Education and Information Technologies	2
Linguistics and Education	1
British Journal of Educational Technology	1
European Journal of Education	1
Foreign Language Annals	1
International Journal of Applied Linguistics	1
Journal of Speech, Language, and Hearing Research	1
IEEE Access	1
Reading and Writing	1
Asia-Pacific Educational Research	1
TESOL Quarterly	1
International Multilingual Research Journal	1
The Modern Language Journal	1

As for the distribution of authors by country (Figure 3), the USA ($f=29\%$) and Iran ($f=28\%$) were the countries where the authors were based, together accounting for nearly half of the studies. Taiwan ($f=14\%$) and China (9%) followed these countries, whereas Sri Lanka, Sweden, Japan, and Oman had the lowest frequency value ($f=5$). The findings might suggest that DA has been a research topic of interest to many scholars in different countries, with the majority from the USA and Iran.

Figure 3. Distribution of Authors by Country

Publication years of the included articles were also investigated, and Figure 4 presents the distribution of articles by year. The figure shows that the number of articles has increased since 2022. Accordingly, 2025 was the year when the highest number of articles ($N=7$) appeared. 2 articles were published in 2024, and 3 articles were distributed in 2023 and 2022. This finding might reveal that even though DA has been a research topic investigated for years, 2022 has been the year when DA in the language education setting has started to receive increased attention.

Figure 4. Distribution of Authors by Year

Regarding the methodological aspects, the included studies demonstrated a wide diversity in research design, data collection, and analysis procedures. The majority of the studies employed experimental or quasi-experimental designs, comparing control and experimental groups to examine the effects of DA on diverse dimensions of language learning and development. Some others adopted mixed-methods approaches, including quantitative and qualitative data to gain a more comprehensive understanding of learner development and mediation processes. A smaller number of studies used qualitative or design-based approaches, particularly those aiming to trace learners' microgenetic growth or explore mediation patterns in detail.

In Toth and Davin's study (2016), the focus was theoretical, emphasizing cognitive and social perspectives, including DA in language education. Regalle and Peker (2017), on the other hand, used a mixed-methods design, gathering data from video recordings, questionnaires, and DA scores, and analyzed the results using independent t-tests and interaction analyses. Similarly, Lu and Hu (2019) adopted a quantitative approach, using questionnaires, static assessment, and phonetics-based DA to reveal its predictive power. Karimpour and Behbahani (2024) also adopted a quantitative quasi-experimental research design. They collected data comparing the experimental group and the control group, both of

which were learning the use of English model verbs. The data were analysed through the between-subjects ANOVA test.

Several studies, including those by Infante and Poehner (2021) and Kao and Wu (2022), focused on qualitative analyses of mediated interactions, examining how learners' conceptual understanding evolved through mediational moves. Grapin and Llosa (2022) and Tavakol et al. (2022) also analyzed interactional or task-based data, focusing on learners' proximal development, transfer abilities, and use of English for specific purposes. Employing a qualitative research design, Lam et al. (2024) utilized the performance rating scores of 224 children's mediated learning sessions and analyzed the results with exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses.

In more recent years, research designs have become increasingly technology-integrated. Studies involving mobile technologies (e.g., Behbahani & Karimpour, 2025; Rahmani et al., 2025; Rassaei, 2023; Rezaee et al., 2019) primarily adopted experimental or mixed-methods designs, utilizing mobile-assisted DA (MDA) platforms such as text or voice chat, WhatsApp, and Telegram. Data were typically collected through pre- and post-tests, reciprocity analyses, and performance scores, with statistical analyses (e.g., t-tests, ANOVA) complemented by thematic coding of interactional data.

Similarly, computer-based DA research (e.g., Bashiri & Ebadi, 2025; Jili et al., 2025; Kao & Kuo, 2023; Saeedi & Soltani, 2025; Zhang et al., 2024) employed experimental or mixed-methods designs. These studies leveraged game-based environments, AI-driven DA assessment systems, or chatbot-assisted DA platforms, collecting data from online tasks, questionnaires, and interviews. Statistical techniques such as ANCOVA, Kruskal–Wallis, and Mann–Whitney U tests, along with thematic or conversation analyses, were commonly used to interpret learning potential and mediation patterns.

Finally, design-based and AI-oriented approaches (e.g., Jaganov et al., 2025; Udeshinee et al., 2024) represented the methodological trend. Udeshinee et al. (2024) used a design-based research framework to iteratively examine DA in text-chat settings through conversation and thematic analyses, whereas Jaganov et al. (2025) developed a Large Language Model (LLM)-driven tool, DynaWrite, based on GPT-4o, to explore the potential of AI systems as mediators in DA contexts.

Overall, the methodological aspect of the included studies shows a clear evolution from traditional classroom-based DA research toward technology- and AI-enhanced designs, with increasingly sophisticated quantitative analyses and multimodal data sources complementing qualitative insights into mediation and development.

The last sub-category of the research context included participants, who were investigated under three dimensions: their educational level, language setting, and target language. The participants' educational level in the included studies (Figure 5) displayed a quite balanced distribution across different levels of education, such as university (N=5), language school and high school (N=4), and young learners (N=3). Yet, the language setting (Figure 6) was mainly limited to FL (foreign language), complemented with SL (second language) and ML (mother language) settings. As for the target languages (Figure 7), English was the primary language in most studies (N=17), while one study included French language learners and one study involved Chinese language learners. In brief, the profile of the participants showed that although their educational levels were balanced, the primary focus on FL and English defined the scope of the included studies.

Figure 5. Participants' Educational Level

Figure 6. Language Setting

Figure 7. Target Languages

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This systematic review aimed to present an overview of studies grounded in DA and language education. To achieve this, it included 20 articles indexed in SSCI, SSCI-expanded, or AHCI, published between 2015 and 2025. These articles were meticulously selected following the PRISMA framework (Page et al., 2021) and the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and coded under themes using the PICO guidance (Chong & Plonsky, 2021). The coding section was primarily based on the research context of the included studies, examining their journal, years, countries, research design, data collection and analysis methods, and participants.

The findings showed that the included studies were distributed across different journals, with four articles published in *Computer-Assisted Language Learning*, the journal with the highest number of articles. 2022 marked the year when DA in the language education context received attention, and 2025 was the year when the highest number of articles was published. Although the selected articles were distributed across different countries, the USA and Iran constituted the majority. Mixed-methods and experimental research designs were mainly adopted. For that purpose, pre- and post-tests and interviews were primary data collection tools, and the gathered data were analyzed through statistical tests (e.g., ANOVA, ANCOVA, t-tests) and thematic coding. The participants in the included articles displayed diversity in terms of their educational level. However, their language setting and target language were not varied; they were mainly in a foreign language setting, with English constituting the majority.

This systematic review differs from previous ones by going beyond specific skills, such as reading and vocabulary (Dixon et al., 2022, 2023; Xia et al., 2024). Moreover, Li and Li (2015) mainly focused on the thematic analysis of the included studies' findings in their review, but the current review involved more recent articles, published between 2015 and 2025, and contributed to the literature by presenting an overview of the included studies' research contexts, as described above.

The overall synthesis of research contexts across the selected studies presented several significant patterns in DA-oriented language education studies. First, the majority of mixed-methods and experimental research designs might aim to quantify research results, present more empirical findings, and triangulate the results. Yet, to analyze the interaction patterns and microgenesis development of the learners, particularly in interaction DA settings, more quantitative and conservation analysis-oriented studies are needed in the field. Second, there was a growing tendency to blend DA-oriented language education with technology, including mobile, computer, and AI technologies. This turning point had the potential to illustrate the contributions of this integration, which could be particularly useful for teachers and teacher candidates who would use DA in their classroom contexts. Despite the initial findings in this field, more studies are needed to explore technology-based DA in language education and its hybrid version, as well as to compare human-driven DA sessions with technology-oriented ones, which would provide more empirical findings. Third, 2022 marked the year when DA received increased attention from scholars. This might stem from the birth of AI technologies, which could offer personalized, real-time, and adaptive feedback (Barrot, 2023). The benefits of AI technologies are also related to the principles of DA; therefore, more studies are needed to explore their integration with DA-based language education settings. Lastly, although the participants' educational levels were diverse, their language settings were mainly limited to a foreign language, with English as the primary target language. This might limit the interpretability and generalizability of the findings. Therefore, more studies are needed to search for DA in different language education settings, including second language, academic language, and language for specific purposes, among others. Furthermore, exploring languages other than English would present more solid contributions to the literature.

This systematic review has some implications. Future studies might focus on the gaps in the included studies in this review. Accordingly, more qualitative and conversation analysis studies are needed to present the language patterns when learners show microgenesis growth or resist change. Comparing human-mediated moves with technology-driven mediation moves would also contribute to the field. Lastly, including languages other than English and different learning settings would provide a detailed understanding of the topic.

Despite the contributions, this review is not without limitations. First, the review merely focused on the WoS research database and included studies indexed in SSCI, SSCI-expanded, and AHCI. This might limit the inclusion of more studies conducted in DA-based language education. Second, this review provided thematic coding of the selected studies' research context but did not encompass their findings. These limitations might also be research topics for potential future reviews.

DISCLOSURE OF AI USE: Grammarly Pro was utilized for language editing services.

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